

THE ROLE OF THE HUMAN FACTOR IN THE PROCESS OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11633457>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 06th June 2024

Accepted: 12th June 2024

Online: 13th June 2024

KEYWORDS

Stability, development, creation, stereotype, event, dialectic, individuals, nations, states, consequence, theory, practice, philosophy, essence, society, modernization, history, system, social, cultural, processes.

ABSTRACT

In the article, general understanding and intuition are insufficient at a certain stage of the development of social relations, which is confirmed by the fact that public processes are not managed by incompetent individuals. Therefore, the desire of scientists and experts to create governance structures is widespread, that is, a community of professionals related to human activity, hoping to solve global problems, because it is understood that they act best in a stable, unstable world. A person with information gradually becomes not only a factor, but also a creator of history. Therefore, in this chapter, we reveal the position of the risk factor, which manifests itself in the instability of economic and political stability.

Methodology to solve the problems of social processes and acts as an action aimed at achieving certain results. Methodological approaches do not create ready-made truths, but define ways to achieve them, allow us to adapt to events in the stable world and make decisions. At the same time, the main task of the methodology is to regulate the forms of theoretical and scientific activity. The application of the methodology creates an opportunity to distinguish the object of social analysis from the diversity of society, to determine its essence, main characteristics, directions of development, as well as human influence on it in socio-cultural activities.

Factors of stability and instability in creative activity

The subjective moment of creation is a person's world, involves a sense of openness to the pressing problems of reality. Subjective factors of creativity include:

- to overcome the barrier of stereotypes of a person, as a creator, innovator willingness to manifest;
- psychological inclination to creativity, the ability to think and act independently;
- initiative, ability to constantly look for new solutions, critical assessment of the situation and on this basis, the ability to create a model of actions to be implemented later;
- human creative acquisition and applicable knowledge.

The main indicator of an active life position is a person's awareness of his own needs and responsibility and participation in the solution of socially important problems, dissatisfaction with himself and, on this basis, he shows a sense of his development prospects.

—The role of the human factor in the process of creative activity is manifested in the growth of knowledge, which expands the possibilities of choosing the methods of activity||54, in strengthening the division of labor, as a result of the specialization of cooperation and social production that increases the number of solutions, their assessment and various analytical abilities are manifested.

In this case, when analyzing information and the main place in determining the direction of action belongs to the individual. Decision-making is always a creative act aimed at resolving the conflict between the existence and the belonging of an object, designed to satisfy ever-growing social and personal needs.

According to N. Shermukhamedova, the basis of the structure of creativity is material and constitutes a dialectical transition between the ideal, the objective and the subjective. A goal, a task, an expectation of a real result - this is an ideal model. In it, an ideal image is built in accordance with the internal logic of the object's development. At the same time, the ideal image contains elements of novelty in relation to the past and present state of the object.

Here the unity of opposites is manifested, a strict scheme subordinated to the logic of the development of the object, and through its improvement, the free, unique development of this object is manifested. Thus, creativity includes both the internal logic and innovative elements of the development of subjects of the subject's activity. A concrete analysis of creativity shows that the emergence of an idea, setting a goal is not arbitrary, but arises from the needs of practice, for example, production, specific organization of business, public and personal interest are among them. On the one hand, creativity is a free human activity, on the other hand, it is determined by the state of the object, nature and society.

Therefore, creativity is a condition of highly effective activity, a person and is considered as the driving force of the development of the society. Creative problem solving differs from mechanical activity not only in freedom of choice, but also in a greater or lesser degree of risk. In contrast to external influences, internal influences require adaptation to the situation. At the same time, dangerous activity goes from a series of protected phenomena to a socio-psychological and economic necessity.

Creativity- this stagnation is the area of transition to the desired area of stability, but it leads to instability. Thus, creativity appears as a constant change, moving from stability to instability and vice versa and so on.

Nowadays, it is generally accepted that absolute safety cannot be achieved, but the psychological perception of the concept of acceptable risk is sometimes still difficult. This may be due to the overstating of statistical data in the analysis and the vague terminology used in the consideration of acceptable risk. The activity is absolute There are also certain psychological difficulties in relation to the risks associated with new fields. The public may express some concern with conventional activities and accept them, but often reject the same or even lower levels of risk that arise in new areas of activity. For example, it is the attitude of public opinion to the development of nuclear energy, which leads to the emergence of

qualitatively new sources of potential danger. According to Z. Kadirova, "the creative process is the modeling of effective activity, where both algorithms and disasters find their place, as a result of which (the highest indicator of creativity) the unexpected becomes inevitable."

Therefore, it is acceptable in relation to new areas of human activity in order to justify the level of risk, it is necessary to find the minimum conditions for the sum of costs to achieve a certain level of safety and losses due to insufficient protection against the effects of a hazardous source. The conditions of minimum risk can be found by analyzing the scale of risk in modern human life. This idea is based on the recognition of self-realized trends in society, which requires establishing an optimal balance between benefits and costs for various activities. Society moves toward balance through experimentation, trial, error, and consistent correction.

Therefore, analysis of the causes of critical situations, "acceptable level of risk" and it is necessary to determine the ability to manage situations involving risk. Tasks related to the management of situations involving risk are very difficult for the following reasons:

- risk factors and the incompleteness of our knowledge of the possible consequences;
- the uncertainty of many situations of risk and benefit;
- the limitations of our capabilities (technical, financial, etc.) in relation to the number of existing or at least known sources of danger;
- assessing the subjectivity of our perception of instability and the degree of its importance;
- the tendency of the "average" person to be less concerned with the potential possibilities of instability, they how far it goes in time;
- interested parties and that there is no uniform approach to the problem of risk management even among organizations;
- measures to reduce the level of risk in some cases net increase due to

It should be noted that our goal is structural-logical, methodological analysis of instability in creativity and not to determine the level of its acceptance in specific situations, this is the task of separate, special branches of science.

Any type of human activity is subject to some degree of instability, which can result in injury, illness, and death. As a rule, the use of any technology, the emergence of new types of activities not only bring additional benefits to society, but also to some extent also defines risk. Social processes have a probabilistic nature, so they show uncertainty of one degree or another. Therefore, the problem of decision-making has a specific philosophical meaning, because it can be formulated as a problem of free will: whether a person can make a conscious decision or not, because all his decisions and practical steps are predetermined. The problem of choice arises when one of many possibilities is chosen, that is, the possibility that allows the subject to achieve the highest efficiency of his actions, that is, when he presents the desired choice.

According to U. Makhkamov, human actions in the process of activity are determined by the outside world, and from object to subject and from subject to object, human influence on the surrounding world when it appears, the activity of the subject in the labor process is

manifested||57. The dialectic of object and subject operates in the choice of opportunity, which defines the problem of choice. Since possibility grows out of the dialectic of necessity and chance, it is necessary to find and define ways of realizing necessity with the limit of maximum possibility. In this case, the object forms and creates opportunities, the subject chooses and implements them in the course of his activity.

Due to the expansion of the field of human activity during the scientific and technical revolution, technical, organizational and the multiplicity of economic solutions increases, the importance of choosing opportunities increases, and the responsibility for the way they are implemented increases. As the scale of production expands and the amount of capital investment increases, the "cost" of any decision in the field of economic education increases. At the same time, it is important to correlate the magnitude of the known risk with that of the less known, and at the same time to inform people of

known to themselves. The task of forcing a new look at existing risks is difficult to achieve clearly due to the irrational and subjective perception of a person. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a practically acceptable and comprehensively based set of quantitative criteria for risk acceptance to take into account social needs, personal preferences and preferences, social justice requirements, economic, political and other aspects, which is a difficult but achievable task. New documents of economic laws removed a significant part of the legacy of all restrictions on economic initiative and entrepreneurship. In order for these assumptions to be acceptable in practice, the following facts and circumstances should be taken into account:

- element of risk provide adequate information on all matters related to the circumstances involved;
- instability problems development of proposals for alternative solutions;
- to prevent instability or eliminate its consequences integrated use of all available tools;
- special information designed to provide the population with the necessary information about actions in dangerous situations in order to minimize its consequences development and implementation of targeted programs.

Some types of activities in real life when implementing, the subject may encounter situations that do not have a clear solution. They can be called unstable. It arises where there is uncertainty when it is necessary to choose an alternative to instability. But a situation of dangerous instability and uncertainty are not the same process.

uncertainty, It exists when neither the nature, nor the number of possible solutions, nor the results of the proposed options are known, that is, when the probability of the occurrence of an event cannot be established, and when the event is completely unexpected and unpredictable.

Instability occurs when the development of events from the stage of uncertainty enters the stage of instability and the need for choice arises, instability is chosen when something is at stake. Anyone who wants to run a healthy business needs to consider risk.

Economists do not accept risk because they are not responsible for the losses that may occur due to risk acceptance. the period of time cannot be precisely determined, therefore, there is no conclusion about mismanagement and abuse.

Currently in business practice this happens on the basis of subjective evaluation, therefore, an uncertain environment is created for managers, which leads them to believe that it is better to act without any risk. As a result of taking a certain risk in their decisions, there will be losses due to reasons that are not related to the actions of the entrepreneur and cannot be predicted, they will not only displease subordinates, but will also be criticized in print and on television.

As a result, economists they feel that they do not feel the moral and material support necessary for their work. True, the new legislation of Uzbekistan excludes criminal liability in the event of a reasonable industrial or professional risk. In other words, the zealous owner who takes risks is no longer seen as a criminal.

Thus, applying the risk and the right to use it allows production to be organized within the most optimal (both from the point of view of the entrepreneur and society) limits. It allows the freest direction in the conditions of stable and unstable reality and can be evaluated quantitatively and qualitatively.

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